

Crafting Connections Between Emotions and Materiality

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Abstract: This paper aims to discuss the idea of craft as a vehicle for processing and expressing emotions through the hands. The task will be approached by introducing the project *Power of Everyday Life*, which includes an exhibition as well as the creative processes of the ten participating artists. We propose that both the process of crafting and the artefacts produced are connected strongly to the meanings of touching and feeling. This in turn is both consciously and subconsciously connected to emotions. Craft can be called 'thinking through one's hands' as it involves both intellectual and physical action often built up by repetitious movement and time consuming labour. Both our intellectual and physical activities unintentionally provoke our emotions. In the process of making, intimate emotions can also be provoked consciously by dissembling them into physical processes that remind the body and mind of the emotions experienced. We conclude the paper by bringing out the value of tactility and its connection to intimacy as well as by pointing out the appearance of emotion in the bodily experience of crafting.

Key words: *Craft, Art, Exhibition, Emotion, Tactility.*

1. Introduction

This paper aims to discuss the idea of craft as a vehicle for processing and expressing emotions through the hands. In our society, where tactility is often overruled by visuality, craft can serve as a reflector of intimacy and emotions. We will approach the task by introducing the case study *Power of Everyday Life*, which includes an exhibition as well as the creative processes of the participating artists.

A group of ten female artists who work in the field of material-based art, using ceramics, glass and textile as their mediums, were invited to create an exhibition at the Museum of Gallen-Kallela, Finland, in 2010. The exhibition holds two themes. The contemporary works of art specifically produced for this exhibition converse with both art and design works done by Akseli Gallen-Kallela (1865-1931), one of Finland's most renowned artists of the National Romantic era. The other theme is to comment upon Mary Gallen-Kallela's (1868-1946) role as the executor of her husband's artistic products as well as her role as the person in charge of everyday life in the artist family.

The artists were invited to be Mary's 'guests' in the museum which not only holds Gallen-Kallela's artistic production and the family's personal artefacts but also was atelier and home for the Gallen-Kallela family. The

exhibition displays works of art, bringing with them the meanings and processes connected. The essential themes are thus everyday life, making with one's hands and relations with the materials used.

We will first frame the case by presenting the main steps and themes of the project *Power of Everyday Life*. After this, we will take a closer look at Gallen-Kallela's connections to the fields of art, craft and design. Then, we will look at the works of art produced for the exhibition, processes related to the making of these works and the multiple ways in which emotions appear both in these processes and the final works. Finally, we will conclude the paper by bringing out the value of tactility and its connection to intimacy as well as by pointing out the appearance of emotion in the bodily experience of crafting.

2. Power of Everyday Life

The project was conducted in collaboration with the Gallen-Kallela museum. The museum, situated near Helsinki, Finland, also served as the site for the actual exhibition. The co-author of this paper, Maarit Mäkelä, acted as an author and curator for the entire project. After negotiating the collaboration with the museum and framing the main lines, the curator invited 9 other artists to participate in the project. The initialisation of the project included several ways in which artists were introduced to the historical context. In the beginning of the project, all artists familiarised themselves with the life of the Gallen-Kallela family by reading several literary sources. Two sources shared by everybody were: an article dealing with the life of Mary Gallen-Kallela [1], and a study about the craft and design works done by Akseli Gallen-Kallela [2].

In addition, the personnel of the museum presented slide-shows related to the story of the family as well as the craft and design sketches and works done by Akseli. We also had an opportunity to visit the museum archive, where we could explore not only paintings, prints, drawings, sketches and prototypes made by Akseli, but also different kinds of everyday objects related to the Gallen-Kallela family life. We were also familiarised with the history and spatial design of the Tarvaspää building – the museum where the exhibition *Power of Everyday Life* was going to take place between February 6 and April 31, 2010. The building is a former home and studio of Akseli and his family, designed by the maestro himself.

Each artist chose a viewpoint on the theme based on everything they experienced and saw during the initialisation of the project: some of the artists were inspired by a specific work or sketch, some wanted to make a site-specific work for Tarvaspää, and some were set upon commenting upon the story of the family with their works. All artists found different aspects that relate to their own life, current emotions or points of interest.

The artistic processes related to this project can be briefly divided into three phases: getting to know the history, processing the information through one's own ideas, and producing the work reflecting the phases above. When the artists were proceeding with their ideas, the curator and the photographer visited the studios. The curator interviewed the artist while the photographer documented the visits by videotaping and photographing. The video was edited to focus on the working processes and the main ideas of each artist's works and was then presented as a part of the exhibition. This material also served as data for exhibition publication as well as background information for this paper. In this paper, we discuss the works and creative processes of four exhibition artists: Riikka Latva-Somppi, Niran Baibulat, Silja Puranen and Maarit Mäkelä.

3. Melding Making and Telling

Akseli Gallen-Kallela was a fine artist, graphic artist, architect and a pioneer of applied art. Although he was very productive, the family's financial situation was always overshadowed by scarcity. Therefore, it was natural for Mary Gallen-Kallela to create her husband's textile designs herself. She would dye fabrics and yarn to make pillows and weave textiles. She also assisted by fabricating clothing for the models and even modelling herself when needed.

In Mary's era, handicrafts were not separated from other household chores. Industrialisation and structural changes in society have subsequently diminished handicraft's role as a means of creating household necessities and ways of economic survival. Simultaneously, the nature of crafts has changed from copying the old to creating the new. Traditionally, handicrafts have been associated with women. Femininity is also present in handicrafts in an apparent way. Although handicrafts were for a long time a gender-bound obligation, they also provided a chance to express one's artistic creativity.

It is said that handicrafts are based on tacit knowledge [3, p. 147] which is essentially present in contemporary craft and material-based art including textile, ceramic and glass art. Within the past few years, the works of material-based art have also assumed a significant role as a part of the contemporary art field. Fundamental elements of traditional handicrafts, such as craft skill, usability and decoration are still used in material-based art. On the other hand, the basic elements of fine art are considered to be expression, aesthetics, conceptuality and interpretation. When trying to define distinctive features of conventional craft and craft with more expressive content, Ihatsu states that the latter has broken away from potential functionality and instead emphasises contextual aspects with experimentation, conceptualisation and narrative elements [4, p. 15].

In the exhibition *Power of Everyday Life*, Mary's role and the appearance of Akseli's emotions in his artistic production offered perspectives through which contemporary artists were able to navigate and restructure their own emotions. German philosopher and sociologist Walter Benjamin (1892-1940) has stated that crafting is related to storytelling as crafting melds making and telling, the object and subject [5, p. 11]. This comprehension is clearly present in the following chapters in which we discuss the contradicting sentiments in everyday family life of both past and present, and the way this resonates in the contemporary work produced. We begin by presenting the work of Riikka Latva-Somppi, co-author of this paper.

4. Mediating Narratives

4.1. Confronting Emotions

Latva-Somppi's work *Eternal Bond* dedicates a high, white, round room to the emotions of loss and grief. In the space in which the installation is built, the ceiling is a high dome, and a tall window lets in natural light. The space reproduces the sacred space around Latva-Somppi's installation. She states that the hall is a metaphor for a mental space where grief is present. With regard to mourning in everyday activities, it is not a state to be lingered in, but more like a hall, a room one walks through several times a day.

Figure 1. Riikka Latva-Somppi's installation in The Gallen-Kallela Museum

It has been suggested that what is meaningful to us depends on our life situation [6, p. 341]. Akseli's and Mary's first-born child, Marjatta, passed away at the age of three in 1895. Through her work, Latva-Somppi reflects the motherly emotions of Mary with her own, herself a daughter who has recently lost her mother. Latva-Somppi was drawn to Akseli's woodcut graphics *The Flower of Death* as the water draws a little girl to pick the flower of death in the graphics. What are left after the death of a close family member are memories and emotions, reflections of self. In Latva-Somppi's installation, the pond is formed by almost three hundred solid glass tears that seem to descend from heaven. The tears are tied together with crocheted silk yarn, to form a thin but extremely strong tie between generations: a tie that becomes visible only through loss.

Figure 2. Akseli Gallen-Kallela's graphics Flower of Death, 1895

Akseli's work was also affected by his fatherly feelings of grief. A small poem of death is written on the graphics. Akseli writes: "The words were my own, they were born, by themselves as I carved out the image with tears in my heart" [7, p. 107]. Just as Akseli, Latva-Somppi created her works just after her mother's death. She particularly chose time-consuming techniques to form the work. Time spent crocheting was essential. A thin silk yarn, depicting purity, truth and fragility would not support the glass tears. A simple solution such as using fishing line would seem too easy. She says: "I hope that people who are familiar with handicrafts will sense the time I have spent crocheting my grief into the silk yarn".

Dutch art historian Liesbeth den Besten has remarked that hands are the most sensitive part of our body and hence the most important organ to physically investigate our surroundings. Our fingertips are the centre of many nerves and thus our hands are able to touch, feel, manipulate and handle materials and tools [8, p. 15; 9, p. 53-54]. den Besten proposes that there is a direct linear connection between the hand, skill and craft, and therefore we are able to think through our hands. She also claims that until recently the brain behind the design has been accorded greater esteem than the hands that realize it, and only recently have we begun to understand how we actually rely on "the haptic repository within the body". [8, p. 15]

According to den Besten, craft is also about the ability to develop one's own materials, techniques and knowledge, with which one can then create meaning and appeal to an observer to become involved and create her own stories. Therefore, the meaning of skill is more in mediating what one has to tell than in maintaining traditional techniques and materials. As den Besten has argued, and seems to be evident also in the case of Latva-Somppi's work *Eternal Bond*, the meaning of this work is in the human touch, in the immanent factors of time and dedication, and in the stories they evoke. [8, p. 18-21]

The physical act of glass forming is, in contrast to crocheting, a fast and very physical way of forming material. For Latva-Somppi, this was yet another way of dealing with her personal feelings of loss during the fabrication of the artwork. Every object produced related to the work *Eternal Bond* brought sweat and tired her muscles. Repeatedly forming the glass tears in the hot and noisy glass studio helped make her emotions concrete and receive a physical form, which, she says, was relieving. She states that as there was a therapeutic dimension in the process of making, providing intimate feelings through work that involves media that people have a physical experience of may also help the recipient confront his or her personal emotions.

Danish craft theorist Louise Mazanti has proposed that skill is an ability to transfer human-existential sensitivity and experience into objects. She claims that, at the level of content or the message, transferring human experience, there is no difference in craft-objects and other artistic expressions: it is the skill of the gifted artist that has the ability to sense and transfer human experience in a convincing and engaging way. In Latva-Somppi's case, skill can be understood as a medium – a tool for communication. As Mazanti has suggested, to communicate in a precise way simply implies the ability to produce an object that carries the artistic intentions and materializes the profundity of the thought. [10 p. 41]

Finnish craft researcher Anna-Marja Ihatsu has stated that conventional craft communicates directly with the user by function and skill, whereas content-oriented craft resorts to personal emotions. Because the public today is more open to discovering the messages of crafted objects in general, the importance of objects as a medium for communication between the maker and the recipient has increased. Where conventional craft leaves little room for questions, personal interpretations and suppositions, content-oriented craft may raise many questions, even leading a person into a state in which they can process some of the fundamental questions of life. [11, p. 181-182]

4.2. Everyday Objects in Transformation

Some of the artists, such as Niran Baibulat, chose to portray the everyday through representing familiar day-to-day objects in transformation. Her work comments upon the contradicting emotions of daily routines. She builds a site-specific textile installation in Gallen-Kallela's bathroom in which the cumulative chaos of ever-growing piles of laundry is organised and colour-coded to form an according language with the bathrooms blue and white tiles. The bathroom, an intimate place for cleaning routines, is now used as a canvas on which the image of everyday life builds.

In her artist interview, she clearly states that she knows the already loaded content of the materials used. An ideal, where everything has its place and order, is formed by neatly folded shirts and underwear, our second skin. The exact stacks of material also refer to the expectations and ambitions we have regarding keeping our homes immaculate and well organised. Through these bodily metaphors of repetitiousness and even boringness, the emotions of daily routines become tangible. Folded clothes form the water in the bath tub and the sink to extend the monotonous tile pattern to all horizontal surfaces. The wavy surface of blue textiles in the bath tub may also contain a hint of escapism: a hope of being able to dive into the depths of the water, relax and forget routines.

That which links craft and emotion is presented in this work through the language of everyday life. Time and repetition are essential with dealing with emotions. A repetitious chore provides a mental space to handle emotions. The unending task of folding and organizing is a way of crafting emotion in everyday life similar to a craftsman's state of production, often referred to as a meditative state. As jewellery artist Dorothea Prühl puts it: "Craft is anti-acceleration... If I want to make an object, it will take time. The process is toilsome. I believe that one can't do anything good without contemplation, without occupying myself with the object in a contemplative way... Therefore, I have to devote my attention to the material and to the possibilities of craft." [12, p. 24]

Figure 3. Niran Baibulat's installation in the exhibition Power of Everyday Life in The Gallen-Kallela Museum

German craft journal editor and curator Gabi Dewald has pointed out that all this takes time. The process of hand-making also takes the maker away from the flow and the rhythm of the daily stream, and in this way, drops one out of time. This, according to Dewald, is actually a requirement of the process of crafting. [12, p. 25] Ceramic artist Maarit Mäkelä, too, refers to this moment in her working diary: "Physical work has begun – apparently with a slow process during which I take the material into my possession both physically and mentally. The process has a meaning like a ritual. My working methods are simple. I use as simple tools as possible and touch the material a lot... This is a rite, an initiation rite during which I move from the level of (logical) thinking to an intuitive and physical mode of working. [13, p. 64]

The relation between thinking and intuition also has a central role in the discussion of Dutch industrial designer Marieke H. Sonneveld and researcher Hendrik N. J. Schifferstein, who have used the term 'gut feelings' as the basic concept for emotions and feelings experienced in tactual interaction. According to their definition, 'gut feelings' are characterized as feelings that emerge from a non-reflective, direct interaction with the world. Rather than being related to our cognitive orientation to the world, which is grounded in our thoughts, these feelings are related to our intuitive orientation and grounded in our physical actions and psychological reactions. The interface of touch and feeling appears thus for them to be a non-verbal, intuitive mode of interaction. [9, p. 62]

In her working process, Baibulat manipulated a large amount of old cloths and transformed them into a spatial installation. She spent frequent days in the museum testing her ideas, trying her colour-coded and ironed textiles in different positions in the space. In this way, she was interacting not only with the recycled textiles, but also with a certain space in an intuitive mode. In her work, Baibulat links the crafting process to the craft of everyday

through time-consuming processes, repetition and the tactual senses of the material. These are also the elements that are present in daily life and household chores – especially in the sphere of a housewife.

4.3. Significant Stitch

It is obvious that the gender roles were strongly present in Gallen-Kallela's epoch. Where Akseli expressed himself by painting, Mary would rather hold a sewing needle than a painting brush. Craft researcher Glenn Adamson also reminds us that craft has been understood as a strategy, through which feminist artists have expressed themselves. He refers to the ideas of Judy Chicago, the pioneer of American feminist art, who proposes that: "Women had been embedded in houses for centuries and had quilted, sewed, baked, cooked, decorated and nested their creative energies away... Could the same activities women had used in life be transformed into the means of making art?" [14, p. 154]

Silja Puranen's work, too, participates in the gender discussion by using sewing as a metaphor for womanhood. A moving image of anonymous female hands incessantly sewing is reflected on a white tablecloth. Puranen's work appears as an endless act of impersonal marking, which results in a white square on a white cloth. The viewer looks at a familiar act of sewing resulting in a needlework that could have been made by anyone.

In addition to the video, Puranen has placed an unfinished needlepoint work in the exhibition. The artist has reproduced Akseli Gallen-Kallela's painting *Seductress* on a piece of needlepoint fabric. A carefully chosen selection of numerous yarns is set by the painting as the artist invites viewers to participate in recreating the painting with a method familiar to many women and typical to the women of Mary Gallen-Kallela's time. Puranen also relates painting as a masculine art form to needlework, which was suitable as a feminine art form in that epoch. Although transferring the painted image through computer aided methods would certainly have been possible, Puranen has chosen to tediously paint the replica of Akseli's painting onto the needlepoint fabric.

Figures 4. and 5. Silja Puranen's installations in the exhibition Power of Everyday Life

The chosen image leads us to take a stance on the dichotomies of role models offered to women. Akseli, as other male painters, used young females as nude models for their paintings. It seems as if women good enough to be spouses were always more sophisticated – women that could keep their clothes on. An exception in art history

however, can be found in the everyday of the Gallen-Kallela family, where Mary posed nude for some of Akseli's paintings including the ambiguous *Seductress*.

4.4. Made-ness as Passage Between Art and Life

Maarit Mäkelä also chose Akseli Gallen-Kallela's art as the basis for her own work. Mäkelä was intrigued by the mystic painting, *Pain Girl*, of an exhausted nude girl who sits on the Mountain of Pain grinding earthly pains in a vessel on her lap. Gallen-Kallela also made a sketch for a box based on this painting. However, he was not satisfied with the prototype and records in his notes of 1908 "I burned it" [15, p. 297]. Mäkelä therefore takes his action into practice, and literally re-fires the idea of the box into ceramic form.

When talking about objects, Mazanti states that the main point does not lie in whether it is made by hand or not, but in the way that these objects communicate. This requires knowledge about how materials act in order to guide the process into a meaningful expression [10, p. 43] or as Williams puts it: to subordinate materials to symbolism and emotional resonance [5, p. 25]. While setting up the exhibition *Power of Everyday Life*, Gallen-Kallela's unfinished prototype for the *Pain Girl Box* was unexpectedly found. When looking at the box with the eye of the craftsman, it is evident that in this work there is a contradiction between the content and the material, or, more specifically, how skilfully the material is tooled. According to Mäkelä, it is apparent that Gallen-Kallela saw the contradiction between the idea, the chosen material and his own skills, and therefore never finished the wooden prototype.

Figures 6. and 7. Akseli Gallen-Kallela's sketch for the *Pain Girl Box* and painting *Pain Girl*

In Mäkelä's ceramic work, the girl, who in Gallen-Kallela's painting is clearly related to Finnish mythology, leads us to think about the contradicting interpretations of today's femininity. The pain girls of Mäkelä grow from skinny creatures into voluptuous female figures with sensuous half open mouths, balancing on the borderline of pleasure, pain and guilt. The sombre tones of Raku-fired boxes call for mystical interpretations. Mäkelä has added a mysterious touch by placing the boxes in a dark room and adding a vague haze of smoke curling out of the boxes, which are slightly ajar. Yet the fleshy images bring us to wonder what the female pain of today is. A fine line between sensuality and brutality makes us think of the multifaceted roles required from women in the everyday life of the twenty-first century.

Figure 8. Maarit Mäkelä's *Pain Girl Box I*

Mäkelä's *Pain Girl Boxes* are also incomplete objects if we think them as part of the sphere of vessels. While firing, all the boxes have been broken into several pieces. Afterwards the artist has glued the pieces together. Still, as such, they have remained broken vessels. For her, the unexpected marks left on the works during the process of making, the 'friendly flaws' as Peter Dormer would call them, are an essential part of her expression. Via the craggy and imperfect female representations, as a result of putting the broken pieces together, she is able to express her emotions and her own experiences as a woman. What seems to be central here is the artistic intention and the question of how the made objects communicate. This requires knowledge about how materials act in order to guide the process towards a meaningful expression. [see also 10, p. 43]

Mazanti has discussed the meaning of uniqueness, how the being made-ness functions as the passage between art and life. In her opinion, it is exactly being made imperfect that is a passage between a material and an autonomous practice. By being made, an object speaks of its own coming into existence, and thereby transgresses autonomy – simply because it comes into existence as a material fact, an object that belongs to the 'real' material world. Being made is also the process during which every object obtains its own personality: the uniqueness, the unusual, the functional or material imperfection, or the breach with expectations. Mazanti proposes that in this way objects receive their identity and authenticity. This is also the way in which they gain their status as artworks, and from this position they are able to speak, as it were. [10, p. 43]

5. Thinking Through Hands

In his article *On Craft as a Boundary Wrecking Ball* (2005), Henrik Most, a Danish curator in the design field, discusses why the meaning of craft seems to be emphasised and the whole field of craft is recuperating [see also 14, p. 166-167]. He links the evolution of craft to the digitising of the public and private spaces, that is, to the

situation where our concrete and bodily relations are being replaced by social structures constructed through digital media. [16, p. 12-13]

This in turn has led to the fact that the bodily significations have diminished and in a sense the body has been excluded from the physical world at the turn of the century. According to Most, it is nevertheless possible to create a slow, material art requiring time and space and feeling, that insists on the body and vision. As Hungarian Michael Polanyi, who has reasoned the essence of tacit knowledge, has stated, the slowness of things is present in those habits and skills that have been passed through centuries. Most suggests that craft could be interpreted as an imprint left by Homo sapiens and a response to the speed of the life we live in. This makes craft the refuge of vulnerability and fragility – a kind of allegory for what is unique and delicate in humans. [16, p. 15] Ihatsu, too, has discussed craft in relation to virtual realities, but from the point of view of a creator. She believes that craft is an answer to basic human needs, such as self-expression, activation, self-esteem or connection with the nature. She suggests craft as one answer to the negative consequences of hyper-modern ways of life. [11, p. 148]

This is why we feel craft to be so essential today. As Most writes, as “creatures of the caress” with five senses, we are bridging the gap between a digitalised vanishing reality and humanity. [16, p. 15] Vision is often regarded as the most important sense in the Western society [e.g. 17]. Similarly, in the field of art, art forms that are ranked highest in acceptance are founded on feelings of distance, whereas art forms based within reach of touch and contact are regarded as less important [18, p. 231]. However, for example, Michel Serres recognises the importance of tactility, thus elevating touching and feeling. He understands the skin as a blurry, ticklish, fluctuating field where the world and the person meet and mix in varying proportions and ways. Most sees the strength of craft precisely in its ability not to limit but to link the contexts. [16, p. 17]

Both the process of crafting, and the artefacts produced are connected strongly to the meanings of touching and feeling. This in turn is both consciously and subconsciously connected to emotions. Craft can be called thinking through one’s hands as it involves both intellectual and physical action often built up by repetitious movement and time-consuming labour. Both our intellectual and physical activities unintentionally provoke our emotions. In the process of making, intimate emotions can also be provoked consciously by disassembling them into physical processes that remind the body and mind of the emotions experienced.

Similarly, experiencing an artefact can be based on vision and thinking but also regarded as perceiving through the body’s memory. In the exhibition *Power of Everyday Life* the artefacts are present as handmade narratives which tune one into thinking about the various ways in which emotions are present in craft. Material-based art, which often uses craft as a medium, can touch the viewer on a very intimate level, thus providing additional understanding. In this paper, we have discussed how crafting can provide significant content to both the makers and to those whose environment the produced artefacts finally enrich.

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